

openlaws

Deliverable 3.2.d2

Open API interface specification

Co-financed by the European Commission (DG Justice)
under action grant JUST/2013/JCIV/AG
(April 2014 – March 2016)

This publication has been produced with the financial support of the Civil Justice Programme of the European Union.
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JUST/2013/ACTION GRANTS

Grant Agreement Number 4562

Project Start date: 01.04.2014
Project End date: 31.03.2016

Report No. D3.2.d2 – Open API interface specification

Version – 1.0

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Deliverable due date: M07 - 31/10/2014
Deliverable actual date: 07/11/2014

Co-funded by the Civil Justice Programme of the European Union

Document History

Date	Revision	Comments
10/10/2014	0.1	First draft
24/10/2014	0.2	Second draft
07/11/2014	1.0	Final draft after correction by Christian Sageder

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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to make an overview of the technical integration with existing data sources and to define a best practice suggestion for future data sources and connectors that public bodies could consider in case they do not provide access to their data or to adapt the existing connectors.

Additionally, this deliverable describes how the data collected from the several legal data sources could be exposed as a REST API to third party services.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable is principally an output of the activity 3.2 “Data model and interfaces”; aim of the activity is the design of a data model and of open interfaces for the integration of several legal data sources, with a focus on the pilot legal data sources.

The aim of the deliverable is the design of inbound interfaces for the legal data sources in scope of the project, and additionally of outbound interfaces for third parties to access the openlaws.eu platform.

This deliverable is strongly dependent on deliverable “3.2d1 Initial architecture and data model specification”, that has been written in parallel to this document. The selected architecture for the OpenLaws platform is to build a custom application (frontend and backend) based on the Vaadin framework with Neo4J database for persisting the data.

2 Data model

The data model used by the API has been described in deliverable “3.2d1 Initial architecture and data model specification”.

Some elements of the data model related to the integration/API and to the approach will be discussed here:

- External key
- Supermodel and mapping

2.1 External data sources key

The council of the European Union defined through resolutions standard keys to identify uniquely law and case law documents:

- ELI – European Legislation Identifier
- ECLI – European Case Law Identifier

Unfortunately, the adoption of ELI/ECLI is far from complete, and in particular for the pilot law data sources in scope of the project this is the current implementation status:

	ELI	ECLI
European Union	?	Implemented for all courts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Court of Justice • General Court • Civil Service Tribunal
Austria	Not implemented. Will probably be implemented in	The VwGH is starting to use it.

	2015. Open data available.	No connector for the data.
Netherlands	?	Fully implemented, for all courts: http://www.rechtspraak.nl/Uitspraken-en-Registers/Uitspraken/Pages/Volledige-lijst-met-Nederlandse-gerechtscodes.aspx
United Kingdom	Fully implemented http://legislation.gov.uk/{type}/{year}/{natural identifier} example: http://legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/1	Not implemented, no free access: http://www.bailii.org/

2.2 Supermodel and mapping from external data sources

As OpenLaws.EU is a data aggregator, it is necessary to define a supermodel to which all data sources have to be mapped, so that data can be treated homogeneously in the platform.

The supermodel defined for the legal objects is the following:

Field	Neo4J Datatype	Description
openlaws_ID	long (unique)	Unique OpenLaws identifier
datasource	String	Identifying the data source
external_ID	String	The external key of the object that can be used to query the data source
author	String	Author of the legal object, dependent on the data source
name_of_legal_object	String	Title of the legal object, dependent on the data source
type_of_legislation	String	Type of the legal object, dependent on the data source (for instance law, decree, draft, bill), not bound to a specific domain

description	String	Description of the legal object, dependent on the data source
link_to_document	String	HTTP link that can be used to retrieve the data source from the client
date_of_document	String (Date in format YYYY-MM-DD, as no explicit date format is provided in Neo4J)	Date of the legal object, dependent on the data source (for instance date of signature or of publication in official gazette)
date_of_effect	String (Date in format YYYY-MM-DD)	Point in time in which the legal object is valid (or date range in which the legal object is valid? As start date-end date)
version	String	Original or consolidated (field missing in the data model but should probably be added)
language	String (ISO 649-1 – two digit)	Original language of the legal object (field missing in the data model but should probably be added).

The **granularity** of the mapping to this supermodel will be defined for each data source (also depending on the offered API): in general the granularity will be very high, meaning that subdivisions of a legal object (for example: article, paragraph, attachment) will not be represented in this supermodel, but only the high-level object will be mapped (for instance a law, council resolution, decree, bill). For the datasources in scope of the first pilot, a remarkable outlier regarding granularity is the Austrian laws consolidated database, as it uses the subdivisions of a legal object as the main object; entire laws are for instance built “live” when they are requested, composing the several subdivisions.

A mapping is a function that, depending on the data source, will define for each entity provided by the data source how the fields of this entity should be used to fill the fields of an entity of the supermodel given above. There should be a 1:1 correspondence to an entity in OpenLaws and an entity in the data source, although the mapping function will not be reversible (as information will be lost in the mapping).

3 APIs offered by third parties to access third parties data

3.1 Approach and guidelines

The approach for the integration is based on these facts:

- Not all legal data sources provide bulk data access, and if provided it is often to be paid for.
- Access to the data sources is heterogeneous in both the technology to access the data (transport layer: HTTP Client, HTTP REST, Web Service), and the data format (XML with a own XSD schema encoded as CDATA in a Web Service response, MetaLex, HTML).
- All data sources expose an identifier that can be used to access single legal objects
- All data sources expose the possibility for a user to access directly with a browser a legal object using an identifier known to the data source
- Most data sources expose an API to search the legal objects within the data source, although with very different parameters
- Most data sources offer consolidated versions of legal objects, but do not offer delta services (what changed for all legal objects in a body of law since a specific date)

The chosen approach is therefore the following:

- Legal objects will not be replicated to the OpenLaws platform, if not for caching purposes
- Legal objects will be searched online directly on the available data sources search APIs, federating the search results
- Enrichment of legal objects done on the OpenLaws platform will be contained in the OpenLaws platform itself and could be offered in the future with a REST API to third party services

3.2 External data sources by third party and legal object type

In this section the available data sources in scope of the current project is listed, with specific regarding the body of laws, the data format, the type of access, the format offered for direct link to documents, and the license of the data.

3.2.1 Europe: laws – EurLex

Data sources:	Legislation, national execution measures
Data format for mapping:	XML
Access:	Online with webservice (limited

	access) or bulk via FTP
License:	commercial and non-commercial re-use of EUR-Lex data is entirely free under conditions
Direct link to documents:	HTML, PDF, Word, TIFF
Languages:	EN (and translations in other EU languages)

3.2.2 Europe: case law – EUCases

Data sources:	Case law, national case law
Data format for mapping:	XML
Access:	Online with webservice (limited access) or bulk via FTP
License:	HTML, PDF, Word, TIFF
Direct link to documents:	EN (and translations in other EU languages)
Languages:	HTML, PDF, Word, TIFF

3.2.3 Netherlands: laws

Data sources:	Laws of the Kingdom of the Netherlands, Treaties, Circulaires, Royal orders, Ministerial decrees, Administrative policies (beleidsregels)
Data format for mapping:	XML (own XSD schema)
Access:	The Dutch Open Data initiative publishes a Basis Law File (“Basis Wetten Bestand” ¹) with an online Web Service to search and retrieve documents.
License:	Data are licensed with the Creative Commons public domain license ²
Direct link to documents:	Links to the official Dutch Laws website can be built ³
Languages:	NL

¹ <https://data.overheid.nl/data/dataset/basis-wetten-bestand>

² <http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

³ For instance: http://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0003110/geldigheidsdatum_25-10-2014

3.2.4 Netherlands: case law

Data sources:	Rechtspraak.nl is a judiciary consortium providing access to case law
Data format for mapping:	XML (own XSD schema)
Access:	The Dutch Open Data initiative publishes an online Web Service to search and retrieve documents.
License:	?
Direct link to documents:	HTML ⁴
Languages:	NL

3.2.5 United Kingdom: laws

Data sources:	Legislation (several legislation types)
Data format for mapping:	XML, HTML, RDF/XML (including usage of MetaLex vocabulary), Atom
Access:	A online REST API is offered to access the Statute Law Database ⁵
Granularity:	The atomic object used for all the interfaces is an element of the law (an article, a paragraph, or an attachment).
License:	free re-use under the Open Government License (legislation.gov.uk)
Direct link to documents:	HTML, RDF
Languages:	EN

Operations:

Operation	Details
Search	<p>Documentation</p> <p>http://www.legislation.gov.uk/developer/searching</p> <p>Sample search REST URI</p> <p>http://www.legislation.gov.uk/id?title={title}&type={type}&year={year}&number={number}</p>

⁴ HTML manifestations are available through the URI scheme [http://rechtspraak.lawly.nl/ecli/\[ECLI\]](http://rechtspraak.lawly.nl/ecli/[ECLI])

⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/developer/contents>

Get	Documentation http://www.legislation.gov.uk/developer/uris Simple get URI http://www.legislation.gov.uk/id/ukpga/1985/67
-----	--

3.2.6 United Kingdom: case law

Data sources:	Case law
Data format for mapping:	DOC
Access:	No API for automated data access available
License:	free re-use under the Open Government License (judiciary.gov.uk)
Direct link to documents:	DOC, PDF
Languages:	EN

Available on the BAILII website (<http://www.bailii.org/>) or the Judiciary website (<http://www.judiciary.gov.uk/>), unfortunately no API are offered.

3.2.7 Austria: laws

Data sources:	legislation (consolidated federal and regional laws)
Data format for mapping:	XML encoded as CDATA inside a web service response
Access:	Data connector from the Austrian Open Data initiative for national laws Private connector available to OpenLaws for federal and regional laws
Granularity:	The atomic object used for all the interfaces is an element of the law (an article, a paragraph, or an attachment).
License:	open for re-use with the requirement to quote RIS as the source of the data
Direct link to documents:	PDF, HTML, RTF
Languages:	DE (some laws are translated to English but no access is provided)

	through the connector)
--	------------------------

Operations with the public connector:

Operation	Details
Search	<p>Documentation http://data.bka.gv.at/RIS/Documents/RIS_OGD_Dokumentation.pdf http://data.bka.gv.at/RIS/OGDService.wsdl</p> <p>Sample search Web Service Request:</p> <pre><soapenv:Envelope xmlns:soapenv="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/envelope/" xmlns:brlr="http://ris.bka.gv.at/Search/1.3/BrLr"> <soapenv:Header/> <soapenv:Body> <brlr:request> <brlr:application>Br</brlr:application> <brlr:query><![CDATA[<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?> <BrLrSearchRequest xmlns="http://ris.bka.gv.at/Search/1.3/BrLr" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"> <Suchworte xsi:type="AndSearchExpression"> <Expressions xsi:type="ArrayOfSearchExpression"> <SearchExpression xsi:type="PhraseSearchExpression"> <Value>fisch*</Value> </SearchExpression> </Expressions> </Suchworte> <Typ xsi:type="PhraseSearchExpression"> <Value>V</Value> </Typ> <Abschnitt> <NummerVon>1</NummerVon> <BuchstabeVon>a</BuchstabeVon> <NummerBis>5</NummerBis> <BuchstabeBis>c</BuchstabeBis> <Typ>Paragraph</Typ> </Abschnitt> <FassungVom>2013-06-18</FassungVom> <ImRisSeit>Undefined</ImRisSeit> <DokumenteProSeite>Twenty</DokumenteProSeite> <Seitennummer>1</Seitennummer> <Sortierung> <SortDirection>Ascending</SortDirection> <SortedByColumn>Kurzinformation</SortedByColumn> </Sortierung> </BrLrSearchRequest>]]></brlr:query> </brlr:request> </soapenv:Body> </soapenv:Envelope></pre>
Get	<p>Documentation http://data.bka.gv.at/RIS/Documents/RIS_OGD_Dokumentation.pdf http://data.bka.gv.at/RIS/OGDService.wsdl</p> <p>Simple Web Service request to get a part of a document</p>

	<pre> <soap:Envelope xmlns:soap="http://www.w3.org/2003/05/soap- envelope" xmlns:brlr="http://ris.bka.gv.at/Search/1.3/BrLr"> <soap:Header/> <soap:Body> <brlr:getDocument> <!--Optional:--> <brlr:application>Br</brlr:application> <!--Optional:--> <brlr:docId>NOR40059893</brlr:docId> </brlr:getDocument> </soap:Body> </soap:Envelope> </pre>
--	---

3.2.8 Austria: case law

Data sources:	case law (VfGH, VwGH, BVwG, LVwG, OGH, OLG, LG, BG, OPMS, AUSL)
Data format for mapping:	XML encoded as CDATA inside a web service response
Access:	Data connector from the Austrian Open Data initiative
License:	?
Direct link to documents:	PDF, HTML, RTF
Languages:	DE

4 API offered to third parties to access OpenLaws data

4.1 Approach and guidelines

The legal objects contained in OpenLaws (entities of the supermodel defined previously) will also be made available to third parties.

No other OpenLaws objects will be made available to third parties, in particular all the social data and user generated data is not foreseen to be made available to third parties, as it consists in a set of features uniquely distinguishing the OpenLaws platform from others.

Access to the data sources will be restricted to enabled service users through authentication.

4.1.1 Integration approach

The data will be available through a REST API using JSON as data format for responses. As Vaadin is more user interface oriented and is not though as a pure server-side component, the services could be implemented using an Java library (for instance Spring HATEOAS⁶).

4.1.2 Security model

Spring Security will be used, with user data and roles assignments laying in

⁶ <http://projects.spring.io/spring-hateoas/>

Neo4J⁷.

A specific role will be used for users that should be allowed to access externally the API.

4.1.3 Data access policy

Data will be available only online, with no limitation on the requests. For practical purposes, queries returning many data will use pagination, with a parameter to specify the requested page.

4.2 Legal objects API

4.2.1 Search

URI	/rest/api/v1/legal-object?q&datasource&page	
Method	GET	
Parameters	The following parameters can be used:	
	q	The query string to be used for the search
	datasource	A comma separated list of datasource identifications
	page	The requested results page
Return codes	200 success, returns application/json 204 no content, we have not found anything 401 no permission 404 error in parameters (datasource or page do not exist)	
Return data	Returns a JSon structure like this: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prev: URI to previous page, if available • Next: URI to next page, if available • Items: list of search results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ openlaws_ID: id of the legal object ○ datasource: datasource identification ○ external_ID: external id of the legal object for the datasource ○ link_to_document: external link to document ○ name_of_legal_object: title of the legal object ○ self (or link rel get): link to get the object with the rest API 	

⁷ http://docs.spring.io/spring-data/data-neo4j/docs/current/reference/html/#tutorial_security

A sample request/response for this interface is the following:

GET https://openlaws.eu/rest/api/v1/legal-object?q=marriage
<pre>{ "Next": "https://openlaws.eu/rest/api/v1/legal-object?q=marriage&page=2", "Items": [{ "openlaws_ID": 239, "datasource": "EU", ... "self": "https://openlaws.eu/rest/api/v1/legal-object/239" }, ...] }</pre>

4.2.2 Get object

URI	/rest/api/v1/legal-object/{openlaws_ID}		
Method	GET		
Parameters	The following parameters can be used: <table border="1" data-bbox="427 898 1353 958"> <tr> <td>openlaws_ID</td> <td>The ID of the object to be retrieved</td> </tr> </table>	openlaws_ID	The ID of the object to be retrieved
openlaws_ID	The ID of the object to be retrieved		
Return codes	200 success, returns application/json 401 no permission 403 forbidden 404 object does not exist		
Return data	Returns a JSon structure with the supermodel structure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenLaws_ID: id of the legal object • [...all other data from super-model..] • Self: link to the object itself 		

A sample request/response for this interface is the following:

GET https://openlaws.eu/rest/api/v1/legal-object/239
<pre>{ "openlaws_ID": 239, "datasource": "EU", ... "self": " https://openlaws.eu/rest/api/v1/legal-object/239" }</pre>

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